

STABILITY AND ULTIMATE STRENGTH OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PLASTIC PANELS^o

L.-A. SAMUELSON *, P. VESTERGREN **, L. KNUTSSON **,
K.-G. WANGBERG *** and V. GAMZIUKAS **

In the design of aircraft and missile structures in fiber reinforced plastics the policy so far has been to avoid buckling under regular loading conditions. The reason for this is the fact that fiber reinforced plastics currently used are brittle and the existence of high local stresses induced by large lateral deflections was assumed to lead to failure of the structure. The initial purpose of the present investigation was to demonstrate the buckling and post-buckling behavior of thin-walled plate structures under inplane shear or compressive loads and to apply existing theories in order to analyze the stability behavior and the ultimate load. Subsequently a large number of tests have been carried out on stiffened and unstiffened panels under compressive or shear loads and in combination with a lateral pressure.

The experiments showed that certain types of panels may sustain large lateral deflections whereas for others the buckling load may be practically equal to the ultimate load. The theoretical predictions of the stability behavior, e.g. the bifurcation load and the load-deflection characteristics were reasonably close to those determined in the tests. The attempts to predict the ultimate load were in some of the cases less successful. This is due to the fact that the estimation of the maximum stresses in the laminate is done in conjunction with an approximate failure criterion and the results may be uncertain. The overall experience is that fiber reinforced plastics may be efficiently utilized in structures subjected to buckling conditions. Methods are available for analysis of the buckling characteristics and the failure load and as the experience from design in composite materials accumulates, confidence in the methods of analysis will soon reach that of metal design.

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* IFM Akustikbyrå, Stockholm

** The Aeronautical Research Institute of Sweden, FFA, Stockholm

*** SAAB-SCANIA, Aerospace division, Linköping

INTRODUCTION

The development of fiber reinforced plastic materials in particular based on carbon or boron fibers in an epoxy matrix, has made possible a potential weight saving in comparison with conventional materials design. Use of composites in structures which deform heavily due to buckling has so far been restricted primarily due to the fact that composites are fairly brittle and analysis of the failure stress in the buckled configuration is very complex.

The present investigation was initiated in order to study the behavior of CFRP composite panels subjected to buckling conditions and to evaluate the possibilities to predict the stability limit, the postbuckling characteristics and the ultimate load by use of available theoretical and numerical tools, see Refs.[5 - 14]

Originally, a number of tests on thinwalled carbon-epoxy panels in shear were initiated. The results showed that the panels did have considerable postbuckling strength. Due to the favorable results considerable interest developed for the continuation of the investigation and since the start a large number of different panel configurations including stiffened and sandwich panels have been tested in shear, inplane compression and inplane compression in combination with lateral pressure. The testing includes panels with cutouts, I-beams in bending, fatigue cycling of shear panels etc.

Several different aspects specific to fiber reinforced composite materials should be considered such as: The applicability of the classical theory of stability in the presence of coupling between inplane forces and bending, the influence of transverse shear strains, the ultimate load in structures showing considerable postbuckling strength, nonlinear material behavior and sensitivity to initial imperfections, voids and delaminations.

The buckling behavior of plates and shells made of GFRP/CFRP/BFRP has been studied by a number of investigators, Refs.[1, 2, 3], both experimentally and theoretically. In particular Ref.[4] by Almroth gives an evaluation of the state of the art.

Theoretical analysis of composite panels subjected to buckling requires access to computer codes for buckling, postbuckling and strength estimates. A number of such codes have been developed and are currently used in the design of composite structures at FFA and Saab-Scania. The experience gained so far will be summarized below.

Finally, manufacturing procedures are important for the design of economic structures in composite materials and some effort was devoted to the associated problems.

CONCLUSIONS

Use of composite materials in lightweight structures subject to buckling conditions was demonstrated in the present investigation. It was shown that

- * Thinwalled plane panels may show considerable postbuckling strength.
- * For stiffened panels or sandwich plates, the buckling load often is close to the ultimate load.
- * Sandwich panels are often designed not to buckle. In some of the cases studied, buckling was observed and a few panels carried loads significantly higher than the buckling load. The shear stiffness of the core was shown to have a marked influence on the stability characteristics.
- * The scatter in the ultimate load was of the same order as that usually obtained in testing of composite materials.

- * Theoretical methods for buckling analysis of plate structures showed good agreement with experiments with respect to the bifurcation load and the post-buckling behavior. Attempts to predict the ultimate loads were only partially successful. The accuracy may be improved by use of more accurate models.
- * The investigation indicates that the bifurcation load gives a reasonable estimate of the failure load of practical panels. Methods for design of buckling tolerant structures are, however, available if use of a panel structure in the postcritical range should be desired.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Test specimens

A variety of specimens were tested according to Table 1 which summarizes the general properties of the different panels. The following comments may be of interest:

The unstiffened monocoque CFRP panels CMC-1, 2 were designed to study the influence of different stacking sequences on the postbuckling behavior. CM_SC-3, 4 were built as integral hat-stiffened CFRP panels designed to buckle locally in the different parts of the panel. Fairly large overall initial imperfections were obtained in the manufacturing process, but these had little influence on the local buckling characteristics. CFRP panels No. CM C-5 thru 8 had homogeneous rectangular section stiffeners and were subjected to either pure compression or a combination of compression and lateral pressure. Panels No. CSC-9 thru 12 had CFRP facings and a honeycomb core while sandwich panels CSG-13 thru 16 featured different combinations of glass and Kevlar faces and a foam plastics core. The different designs are given in Fig. 1.

Specimens SMC 1 thru 6 used in shear tests comprize a series of monocoque CFRP panels. The length to width ratio of these panels was approximately 5. Specimens 1 thru 3 were designed for testing of the postbuckling behavior and the dependance on the lay up configuration. Specimens 4 thru 6 were intended for a study of the influence of the boundary conditions by use of different types of integral reinforcements around the edges.

Two CFRP sandwich specimens with 5 mm aluminum honeycomb core, SSC-7, 8 were designed not to fail from loss of stability. CFRP specimens SSC-9 thru 11 featured a 2 mm HEXCEL CFRP honeycomb core design and contained cutouts in the FRP reinforced central part of the panel. Fig. 1b.

Fig. 1 a Geometry of compression test specimens

Fig. 1 b Shear test specimen

Fig. 1 c Bending test specimen

SPECIMEN NO	TYPE OF BENDING	DIMENSIONS [mm]				LAY-UP
		L	b	t	c	
CMC- 1		320	350	1.5	-	$[\pm 60_2 / 0_2]_{S12}$
CMC- 2		"	"	"	-	$[0_2 / \pm 60_2]_{S12}$
CM _S C- 3		335	"	2.0	-	$[0_2 / (\pm 45)_2 / 0_2]_{S16}$
CM _S C- 4		"	"	"	-	"
CM _S C- 5		377	"	1.5	-	$[(\pm 45)_2 / 90]_{S10}$
CM _S C- 6		"	"	"	-	"
CM _S C- 7		"	"	"	-	$[(\pm 45)_2 / 45]_{S10}$
CM _S C- 8		"	"	"	-	"
CSC- 9		320	370	1.0	8.0	$[0_2 / 90 / 0 / \mp 45 / 0_2]_{T8}$
CSC-10		"	"	"	"	"
CSC-11		"	"	"	"	"
CSC-12		"	"	"	"	"
CSG-13		820	370	1.0	20	Fabric $[0/90]_{T1}$
CSG-14		"	"	"	"	"
CSG-15		"	"	"	"	"
CSG-16		"	"	"	"	"
SMC- 1		1065	180	1.04	-	$[(\pm 45)_2]_{S8}$
SMC- 2		"	"	1.30	-	$[90 / (\mp 45)_2]_{S10}$
SMC- 3		"	"	1.04	-	$[(90)_2 / (\mp 45)]_{S8}$
SMC- 4		"	190	2.05	-	$[90 / (\mp 45)_3]_{S14}$
SMC- 5		"	"	"	-	"
SMC- 6		"	"	"	-	"
SSC- 7		1065	186	0.60	5.0	$[(\mp 45)_2]_{T4}$
SSC- 8		"	"	0.36	"	$(\mp 45)_{T2}$
SSC- 9		989	190	0.40	2.0	$[\pm 45 / 90]_{T3}$
SSC-10		"	"	0.33	"	"
SSC-11-13	"	"	"	"	"	
BMC- 1		1500	194	2.88	-	$[45 / (\pm 45)_4]_{S18}$
BMC- 2		"	"	3.01	-	"
BMC- 3		"	"	0.65	5.0	$[(\pm 45)]_{S4}$

EXPLANATIONS

Specimen code is as follows: loading/type/material/specimen no
loading is either Compression, Shear or Bending
type of specimen refers to Monocoque, Monocoque with stiffeners or Sandwich
materials are Carbonfiber/epoxy or Glassfiber/polyester
L = length (x-direction), b = width, t = laminate or face thickness
c = core thickness

TABLE 1

Finally, three I-shaped CFRP beams BMC-1 thru 3, Fig. 1c were tested in 3-point bending. These beams were manufactured from two U-beams bonded together and additional reinforcements were added along the flanges. Specimens Nos. 1 and 2 had a monocoque web while No. 3 had a 5 mm aluminum honeycomb core. Specimen BMC-2 contained manufacturing defects which would have caused rejection in normal production.

Test facilities

The compression tests were carried out in standard tensile-compression testing machines available at the FFA. Special arrangements were used to provide well defined boundary conditions. Most of the panels were tested in the device shown in Fig. 2. The horizontal, loaded edges are inserted into a series of cut-open ball bearings which provide conditions very close to simple support, see Ref. [13]. The vertical edges were restrained only in the lateral direction by use of steel rulers. Lateral pressure may be added through use of a rubber bag placed inside the test box. Panels CM_sC-3, 4 and CSG-13 thru 16 had simply supported vertical edges but the loaded edges were 'clamped' according to Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Compression test device

Shear tests are performed in a special loading device, Fig. 3, where a horizontal shear load is transferred to the test specimen through 'cover plates' simulating the skin of an aircraft lifting surface. Rotation of the panel in a vertical plane is restricted by use of supports at the ends. The boundary conditions are not as clearly defined as for the compression panels. Along the horizontal edges rotation is restricted by the cover plate stiffness which may be evaluated in a numerical analysis. The vertical edges were fitted with heavy steel clamps and may thus be regarded as clamped.

Fig. 3 Shear testing device

Finally, the bending tests were carried out in a standard testing machine according to the arrangement indicated in Fig. 1c.

Measurements

In most of the tests, in particular those involving large lateral displacements, the shadow Moiré method was used to visualize the buckling behavior. The fringe patterns were recorded on video tape. The technique proved very useful since it made possible simultaneous readings of displays in addition to registration of various sound effects during the tests. Sharp noises were taken as indications of material failure. Strains were measured in most of the tests in order to estimate stress levels at concentrations and to check that the applied load was uniformly distributed.

Test results

Most of the test results are summarized in Table 2 where the observed buckling loads and the ultimate loads are listed together with comments on initial imperfections, buckling wave number etc. In addition, Figs. 4 and 5 show typical buckling patterns and postbuckling lateral deflection paths determined in the tests.

Various methods may be used to define the buckling load:

- a) the load when lateral deflections are observed visually
- b) the load when strain reversal occurs
- c) the load when the maximum lateral deflection exceeds a certain percentage of a characteristic length and
- d) the point where the total load vs total inplane deflection becomes nonlinear.

In the investigation method a) was used in most cases. However, all methods give results which coincide within a few per cent.

The thinwalled panels, CMC-1, 2 and SMC-1 thru 6, all showed large post-buckling deflections, in some cases of the order of 10-20 times the wall thickness, see Figs. 4a and 5a, b. The integrally stiffened panels CM_sC-3, 4 failed at a load level only slightly higher than the local buckling limit, while panels CM_sC-5 thru 8, which did not buckle locally, sustained a much higher postbuckling load. The reason for this is that local buckling of the hat-stiffened panels induced high local tear stresses which probably initiated the failure.

Sandwich panels, specimens SSC-7,8 did not buckle but failed due to fracture of the face material. Panels CSC-13-16 appeared to fail through core shear instability. The actual cause of failure of the thin core sandwich panel SSC-9-10 was not possible to determine. However, different failure modes may have contributed such as exceedance of the composite material strength (flange) or the core shear instability limit.

The effect of a lateral pressure on the buckling and ultimate loads, specimens CM_sC-6, 8 and CSC-9, 10 was not significant and in some cases the ultimate inplane loads were higher for the panels under lateral pressure.

The scatter obtained in the tests, indicated by the results for specimens SMC-4-6, SSC-9-11 is of the order of 10% of the average values of buckling and ultimate loads respectively.

Results for specimens SSC 12, 13 reflects the residual strength after fatigue cycling according to Table 2. The observed ultimate loads differ for the various panels, and in some cases the residual strength even exceeds the strength of the panels not subjected to fatigue cycling. Whether this is an effect of the fatigue cycling or a 'normal' scatter is not yet clear.

THEORY AND NUMERICAL RESULTS

Prediction of the load carrying capacity of panel structures involves analysis of the stability limit, the postbuckling state and the ultimate load. A large number of papers on these topics are available, see for instance Refs. [15, 16]. A very brief summary of the characteristics of the stability theory as used in the present study will be given.

Methods of analysis

The governing equations for rectangular plates may be deduced from the theory of stationary potential energy. Refs. [1, 15].

$$V = U + \Omega$$

(1)

Fig. 4 Typical buckling characteristics compression loaded panels

SMC-1, 3

SMC-4, 6

BMC-1, 2

Fig. 5 Typical buckling characteristics - shear and bending panels

SPECIMEN NO	EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS				THEORETICAL RESULTS				COMPARISON EXP. - THEORY		
	[mm] max. imp.	P _B [kN]	P _u [kN]	n _{exp}	P _{BIF.} [kN]	P _{u,TH} [kN]	n _{TH}	CODE	P _B / P _{BIF.}	P _u / P _{u,TH}	n _{exp} / n _{TH}
CNC-1	0.60	~1.8	30.0	1	2.2 (~2)*	65	1	STAGSC	0.9	0.5	1
CNC-2	0.25	~1.8	35.0	1	1.8 (~1)*	70	1	--	1.1	0.5	1
CM _s -C-3	7	~100**	130	3**	77** (190)**	-	8(3)	BUCK	0.8	-	1
CM _s -C-4	5	~100**	116	3**	-- --	-	" "	"	0.8	-	1
CM _s -C-5	0.25	80** 100	115	1	94**	(104) ⁺	1	BUCK-STAGSC	0.85	-	1
CM _s -C-6	0.25	100	146	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CM _s -C-7	0.08	115	122	1	143**	(104) ⁺	1	BUCK-STAGSC	0.8	-	1
CM _s -C-8	0.08	105	112	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CSC-9	0.44	210	231	1	219	(219)	1	SOPT	0.96	(1.1)	1
CSC-10	0.48	190	214	1	219	(219)	1	"	0.87	(1.0)	1
CSC-11	0.55	170	196	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CSC-12	0.82	175	186	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CSC-13	~2	-	34	1	42	(42)	1	SOPT	-	(0.81)	1
CSC-14	~2	-	46	1	57	(57)	1	"	-	(0.81)	1
CSC-15	~2	-	46	1	42	(42)	1	"	-	(1.1)	1
CSC-16	~2	-	44	1	42	(42)	1	"	-	(1.1)	1

- * Buckling load nonlinear theory
- ** Interstringer buckling
- + Eulerbuckling regarding stringers only

Table 2 a

SPECIMEN NO	EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS					THEORETICAL RESULTS				COMPARISON EXP. - THEORY				
	[mm] max. imp.	P _B [kN]	P _u [kN]	n	$\frac{P}{weight} \cdot 10^{-7}$	BUCKLING BIFURCATION	LOAD NONLINEAR ANALYSIS	P _u [kN]	n _{TH}	CODE	$\frac{P_B}{P_{BIF.}}$ EXP.	$\frac{P_B}{P_{NONLIN}}$ EXP.	$\frac{P_u}{P_{u,TH}}$ EXP.	$\frac{n_{exp}}{n_{TH}}$
SMC-1	1.0	23	63	6	1.4	32	33	-68	6	STAGSC	0.72	0.70	0.93	1.0
SMC-2	0.5	60	114	6	3.0	47	53	98	5	--	1.28	1.13	1.16	1.2
SMC-3	0.7	45	129	8	2.8	60	45	121	8	--	0.75	1.00	1.07	1.0
SMC-4	-	200	275	5	7.0	280	264	-	5	--	0.71	0.76	-	1.0
SMC-5	-	190	278	5	6.7	268	252	-	5	--	0.71	0.75	-	1.0
SMC-6	-	195	295	5	6.9	236	218	-	5	--	0.83	0.89	-	1.0
SSC-7	-	No buckling	443	-	-	-	-	470	-	SOC	-	-	0.94	-
SSC-8	-	" "	210	-	-	-	-	282	-	--	-	-	0.74	-
SSC-9	-	100	108	1	8.2	177 (101)	-	-	1	STAGSC (SOPT)	0.56(0.99)	-	-	1.0
SSC-10	-	90	97	1	7.4	177 (101)	-	-	1	--	0.51(0.89)	-	-	1.0
SSC-11	-	90	95	1	7.4	177 (101)	-	-	1	--	0.51(0.89)	-	-	1.0
SSC-12	-	No buckling	70	1	-	177 (101)	-	-	1	--	-	-	-	1.0
SSC-13	-	100	113	1	8.2	177 (101)	-	-	1	--	-	-	-	1.0
EMC-1	0.6	92	103	2	2.5	156	-	105	2	STAGSC	0.58	-	0.98	1.0
EMC-2	-	88	121	2	2.4	156	-	105	2	--	0.58	-	0.98	1.0
MSC-3	-	No buckling	106	-	-	-	-	98	-	SOC	-	-	1.28	-

1) P_B/WEIGHT = Ratio between experimental buckling load and weight of 1.0 mm² of buckled area times the thickness.
Density used is 1.6 · 10⁻⁶ kg/mm³

Table 2 b

where

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \iiint (\bar{\sigma}_x \bar{\epsilon}_x + \bar{\sigma}_y \bar{\epsilon}_y + \dots + \tau_{zx} \gamma_{zx}) \, dx \, dy \, dz \quad (2)$$

and

$$\Omega = \iiint \left(\frac{1}{b} p_x, \dots - pw \right) \, dx \, dy \quad (3)$$

Equilibrium requires that

$$\delta V = 0 \quad (4)$$

Introduction of the compatibility and constitutive relations Ref. [16].

$$\epsilon_x = u_{,x} + \frac{1}{2} w_{,x}^2; \quad \kappa_x = -w_{,xx} \dots \quad (5)$$

and

$$\{N\} = [A]\{\epsilon\} + [B]\{\kappa\}; \quad \{M\} = [B]\{\epsilon\} + [D]\{\kappa\} \quad (6)$$

leads to non-linear equilibrium equations of the form

$$\begin{cases} N_{x,x} + N_{xy,y} = 0; & N_{xy,x} + N_{y,y} = 0; \\ M_{x,xx} + 2M_{xy,xy} + M_{y,yy} + N_x w_{,xx} + 2N_{xy} w_{,xy} + N_y w_{,yy} = -p \end{cases} \quad (7 \text{ a-c})$$

Expressed in terms of the displacements u , v and w Eqs (7) take the form

$$L_i(u, v, w, u_{,x}^2, \dots, w_{,x}^2, \dots) = H_i \quad i = 1, 3 \quad (8)$$

The general solution of (8) becomes extremely complicated and is best done by use of a computer.

The stability of the plate may be studied for instance by use of the "Adjacent - Equilibrium criterion". Assume that a new state of equilibrium is given by

$$u = u_0 + \delta u \quad \text{where}$$

u_0 is the fundamental solution given by (8). Then insertion in (7) yields the eigenvalue problem:

Fig. 6 Infinitely long plate subjected to inplane loads

$$\begin{cases} \delta N_{x,x} + \delta N_{xy,y} = 0; & \delta N_{xy,x} + \delta N_{x,y} = 0; \\ \delta M_{x,xy} + 2\delta M_{xy,xy} + \delta M_{x,yy} + N_x \delta w_{,xx} + 2N_{xy} \delta w_{,xy} + N_y \delta w_{,yy} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

As an example, Eqs. (9) were solved for the special problem given in Fig. 6 by assumption of a specific buckling deflection function:

$$\delta w(x, y) = A \cos \frac{\pi y}{b} \sin \frac{\pi}{L} (x - \epsilon_y) \quad (10)$$

The problem may then be reduced to minimization of:

$$\bar{N}_{xy} = \frac{\pi^2}{2\epsilon b^2} \left[D_{11} \left(\frac{b}{L} \right)^2 + 2 \left(D_{12} + 2D_{66} \right) \left(\frac{\epsilon^2 b^2}{L^2} + 1 \right) + D_{22} \left(\frac{b^2}{L^2} \epsilon^4 + \frac{L^2}{b^2} + 6\epsilon^2 \right) - 4D_{16} \frac{\epsilon b^2}{L^2} - 4D_{26} \left(\frac{\epsilon^3 b^2}{L^2} + 3\epsilon \right) + \bar{N}_x \frac{b^2}{\pi^2} + \bar{N}_y \frac{b^2}{\pi^2} \left(\epsilon^2 + \frac{L^2}{b^2} \right) \right] \quad (11)$$

with respect to the wave length parameters ϵ and L .

Typical results, related to the geometry of test specimens No. SMC-1 thru 6 are shown in Fig. 7. Results of this form are of great value for the designer and may be given in graphical form for panels of fixed layup configurations. The theory presented above can of course be extended to other geometries, including stiffened panels and solution of the equations may also be obtained through use of general purpose FEM or similar computer programs.

The general solution that is obtained from (8) for a (initially imperfect) panel is shown in Fig. 8. Estimation of the bifurcation load from the nonlinear analysis usually agrees with the value given by Eq. (11) for flat plates.

The ultimate load of the structure may be estimated by use of some failure criterion. Throughout the present paper Tsai's condition was used:

$$\phi = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_{1f}} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{\rho} \cdot \frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_{1f}} \cdot \frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_{2f}} + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_{2f}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{\tau_{12f}} \right)^2} \quad (12)$$

$\phi \geq 1$ implies failure.

The different computer codes developed by or available to FFA and Saab-Scania are described briefly in Table 3.

Fig. 7 Influence of percentage of 90°-layers on the stability limit - shear load

Fig. 8 Typical load-deflection curves obtained from linear and non-linear theory

COMPUTER CODES FOR STABILITY ANALYSIS		
NAME	REFERENCE	TYPE OF ANALYSIS
KGW003	[17]	for bifurcation analysis of monocoque panels under combined loads (see Figs. 6, 7)
BUCK	[18]	for bifurcation analysis of stiffened panels
SOPT	[19], [20]	for bifurcation analysis and optimization of sandwich panels. Theory includes the shear deformation of the core
STAGSC	[22]	General code for bifurcation and nonlinear analysis of shell structures
BOSOR	[23]	Lockheed program for general shells of revolution. May be applied in certain types of parametric studies for plane panels
ASKA	[24], [25]	Comprehensive FEM code, used by Saab-Scania for general structural analysis including bifurcation of composite panels
SPECIAL PURPOSE TIME SHARING PROGRAMS FOR ANALYSIS OF LAYERED COMPOSITE MATERIALS		
SOC	[19]	Evaluates inplane stresses and strains of laminates
LOPT	[19], [21]	Optimizes the lay-up configuration of laminates subjected to different loading conditions

Table 3

Numerical results and comparisons with experiments

Theoretical values of the buckling and ultimate loads are given in Table 2 where a direct comparison with the experimental results is made. Table 2 also gives the computer codes used in the analyses.

In general, the bifurcation loads agree reasonably well with the test results. Estimation of the buckling load from a nonlinear analysis according to Fig. 8 sometimes yields a better agreement with experiments, partly due to the fact that the procedure simulates closely the procedure used in visual observation of the buckling pattern.

The bifurcation loads obtained by use of STAGS for sandwich panels overestimate the actual loads. However, the SOPT program, which includes the core shear stiffness yields buckling loads in agreement with experiments, Fig. 9 a-c. Moreover, introduction of a stiff core in the SOPT model yields results close to those obtained by use of STAGS.

The influence of the boundary conditions on the bifurcation load is fairly high. Choice of an effective

Fig. 9 a

Fig. 9 b

width of the panel requires experience and a model which includes a part of the surrounding structure would be preferable. The cost of such a model might, particularly for a non-linear analysis, be prohibitive and the need for simplification certainly exists.

Typical buckling patterns determined by use of STAGS are indicated for panel CMC-2 in Fig. 10. It shows that the specific deflection pattern given in Fig. 4 a is closely simulated by the theory. Table 2 lists the half wave numbers obtained theoretically and in the experiments. Good agreement was obtained in all cases.

Analyses of panels in the post-buckling range taking into account the initial imperfections were performed by use of STAGS. Some of the results are included in Figs. 4 and 5. In general the maximum lateral deflection agrees well with the observed experimental behavior. This is also true for the deflection pattern, which may be represented by Fig. 11 for a panel under shear load. The load distribution across panel No. CMC-1 is shown in Fig. 12. In the analysis, uniform displacement of the boundary was prescribed. The postbuckling curves of the shear panels show that the theoretical models used have been too stiff compared to the test specimens, much due to uncertain boundary conditions. At a certain load level, tensile stresses were obtained in the numerical analysis and, hence the results above that level are not reliable for comparison with experiments.

Theoretical estimates of the ultimate load as defined by Eq. (12) were obtained for most of the test specimens and the results are presented in Table 2. It is evident that the predicted failure load for panels which failed below or in the vicinity of the buckling limit agrees well with experiments. The attempts to predict failure load in the postbuckling range was only partially successful. The results for specimens SMC 1-3 indicate an error of ~10% in the predicted failure load which may be regarded as acceptable. However, some adjustments to the assumed boundary conditions had to be made in order to reach that level of accuracy.

Fig. 9 c

Fig. 9 a-c Influence of core stiffness properties on the stability limit

Fig. 10 Theoretical lateral deflection of CMC-2 at 30 kN load. Each line corresponds to a specific level of deflection from 1 to 10 mm

Fig. 11 Lateral deflection pattern of panel SMC-1 at bifurcation load

A few more analyses have been carried out to show the possibilities available in modern computer codes. The results are included in Table 2 and show the potential of modeling by use of FEM techniques.

Specimens CMC-1, 2 failed at a load only 50% of that predicted by the theory. This was due to local crushing of the panel edges in the testing. Use of a finer mesh in the theoretical model would have given a sharper stress concentration at the edges than that given in Fig. 12 and a better agreement could be expected.

Fig. 12 Load distribution across horizontal boundary for panel CMC-1

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